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Climate Change Scepticism in Spain: Are the Political and Ideological Drivers so Important?

Fernando Calonge-Reillo

Abstract:

Amidst mounting evidence of anthropogenic climate change, the prevalence and drivers of denialist and sceptical viewpoints have been a subject of considerable debate, particularly within the United States where political and ideological influences have been emphasised. This study addresses calls to examine the generalisability of this relationship to other contexts, focusing on 'Environment' surveys by the Spanish Centre for Sociological Research's 2010 and 2023. The findings indicate that climate change scepticism remains low in Spain. While a minor recent polarisation is observed, political-ideological affiliation does not appear to be a primary determinant. Instead, environmental beliefs and perceived exposure to environmental problems are identified as the most significant predictors of scepticism. These results highlight the importance of contextualising research on climate change scepticism beyond the US and encourage further investigation across diverse geographical settings.

Keywords:

Climate change scepticism; climate change denial; political factors; environmental beliefs; environmental risk exposure.

1. Introduction:

Research and reports over the past two decades have consistently highlighted a growing tide of climate change denial and scepticism among the public. This trend is particularly striking given the overwhelming scientific consensus on the existence and anthropogenic origin of climate change, along with the fact that the years 2023 and 2024 have seen unprecedented global temperature records (Bevacqua, Schleussner and Zscheischler 2025; World Meteorological Organization 2025). This research has focused largely on the United States, where Republican leaders have been resistant to the global climate change movement since the early 2000s (Borger 2001; Pianin and Goldstein 2001) and where the Trump administration dismantled much of the previous climate policy (Milman, Smith and Carrington 2017; Grobe 2017).

This stance adopted by Republican leaders has reinforced the partisan divide on climate scepticism. As a result, only 28% of Republican supporters, compared to 90% of Democratic supporters, indicated being very worried about climate change in 2023 (Gallup 2024). Moreover, 44% of Republican sympathisers in 2022 denied that climate change was primarily caused by human activity, while this figure was 7% for Democratic sympathisers (Pew Research Center 2022). Given this increasing evidence, much of the scientific literature on climate scepticism has turned to examining its political and ideological underpinnings.

However, international data reveal that levels of climate scepticism are not as pronounced in all countries. For instance, in Brazil, Colombia, France, Germany, Italy, and Japan, more than 90% of respondents indicated in 2023 that climate change was very likely occurring, while in Brazil, Colombia, Mexico, South Korea, and Turkey, less than 20% denied its anthropogenic origins (IPSOS 2024). At the same time, it has been cautioned that ideological and partisan factors may not be the predominant drivers of climate change attitudes in all countries (Lewis, Palm and Feng 2018), suggesting a need for more research beyond the United States and Anglophone nations.

This study responds to such calls on climate change scepticism by investigating its prevalence and evolution in Spain. It addresses three objectives. Firstly, it examines whether climate change scepticism, in its various dimensions, is as prevalent in Spain as it has been shown to be in other countries, particularly those in the Anglosphere. Secondly, it investigates whether political and ideological factors have become increasingly influential in shaping climate scepticism in Spain, as has been observed in Anglophone nations. Finally, it contributes novel evidence on the key determinants of climate scepticism in Spain, where such research remains relatively scarce.

To achieve these objectives, we analysed the 2010 and 2023 'Medio Ambiente' Studies conducted by the Centre for Sociological Research (Spain). These studies incorporated variables summarising the opinions of the Spanish population aged 18 and over regarding environmental problems, their environmental beliefs and attitudes, support for specific environmental policies, and a range of socio-demographic, political, and economic factors.

Descriptive statistics were used to identify the Spanish public's perception of different dimensions of climate change. Hierarchical multiple regression analyses were then conducted to determine how various types of factors, particularly ideological and political ones, contributed to the predictive power of the model to explain climate change scepticism.

2. Theoretical Framework

A reduction in public trust in science and the emergence of negationist and sceptical positions have been evident for several decades (Lloyd, 1996). It has been argued that a continuum of positions exists, rather than a clear dichotomy between negation and trust in science (Aitken et al., 2016), and these positions do not necessarily extend uniformly across all scientific domains (Fuglsang & Losi, 2024). Factors such as trust in regulatory institutions (Aitken et al., 2016), political or ideological biases (Lloyd, 1996; Marteau, 2023; Haglin & Vedlitz, 2023), and the partisan nature of debates, particularly concerning climate change (Aerni, 2016), have been proposed to explain this variability.

Climate change, in particular, has become a highly contentious and debated phenomenon, largely due to ideological and political influences (Miller et al., 2024). The United States has been a primary focus of research on climate change scepticism, driven by evidence of a growing population that doubts the existence and severity of anthropogenic climate change (Smith and Leiserowitz 2015). Numerous studies have highlighted the highly politicized nature of climate scepticism in the US, particularly linked to the Republican Party's adoption of denialist positions (Hahnel, Mumenthaler and Brosch 2020). Research consistently shows that individuals who identify as Republicans are more likely to hold sceptical views (Meyer 2018; Hornsey, Chapman, and Humphrey 2022), and deny climate change impacts and risks (Botzen et al. 2016). Similarly, conservative ideological orientations have been found to be strong predictors of climate scepticism (McCright and Dunlap 2011; Munoz-Carrier, Thomsen and Pickering 2020; Tremoliere and Djeriouat 2021; Pano and Carrus 2019). Furthermore, specific political values and ideologies, such as individualism, libertarianism and support for capitalist industrial systems, have been linked to increased climate scepticism (Stevenson et al. 2014; Matthews 2015; McCright 2016; Santos and Feygina 2017). Past voting behaviour, self-identified political ideology, and broader political and ideological values will be considered by the present article as conditioning factors for climate change scepticism.

While a body of research has highlighted the growth of climate scepticism and the significant role of political factors in predicting it, primarily in the United States, the extent to which these trends are replicated in other sociocultural contexts remains uncertain. Although some studies have suggested that similar patterns may exist in Anglophone countries (Engels et al. 2013), questions remain about their universality. Emerging research has begun to explore these issues in diverse settings, including China (Yang et al. 2021; Liu 2015), Russia (Ashe and Poberezhskaya 2022) and certain Northern European nations (Baiardi and Morana 2021). Moreover, studies from these and other contexts have found that climate scepticism is not always strongly linked to partisan affiliation (Fraembs and Drobic 2024), that social polarisation on this issue may be less pronounced (Leka and Furnham 2024; Boncu et al. 2022), and that the associated debates may be less heated (Engels et al. 2013). Considering these

findings, this article examines whether the pattern of widespread climate scepticism observed in the United States is also evident in Spain, or whether scepticism in this context is closely tied to political and ideological divisions.

This study contributes to addressing the first research question by employing a longitudinal design, drawing on two surveys conducted by the Centre for Sociological Research in 2010 and 2023. This approach helps to rectify the gap identified by Hornsey, Chapman and Humphrey (2022) in the climate scepticism literature, namely the scarcity of studies examining the temporal evolution of climate scepticism. Moreover, this paper explores whether the political determinants of climate scepticism have become more pronounced over time, allowing for a comparison with the broader trends observed in the United States.

This study aims to evaluate the evolving significance of political factors in explaining climate change scepticism. To achieve this, they will be contrasted with the following influential factors that has also being highlighted in the literature.

Thus, sociodemographic factors are often cited as explanations for climate change scepticism. While US and Latin American studies suggest that these factors are not the most decisive, consistent associations have emerged between higher levels of scepticism and male gender (Ecklund et al. 2017; Boncu et al. 2022), older age (Pellegrini and Loner 2024; Fraembs and Drobic 2024), lower education levels (Wang and Kim 2018; Yan, Schroeder and Stier 2022), rural residence (Whitmarsh 2011; Hornsey, Chapman and Humphrey 2022), and smaller household size (March, Saurí and Olcina 2014).

Literature has also highlighted the significance of individuals' perceived behavioural control, or their belief in their personal and collective capacity to address challenges. Specifically, numerous studies have demonstrated that perceiving oneself as capable of effectively influencing environmental outcomes through one's actions is associated with reduced environmental scepticism (Ojala 2015; Haydn and Cook 2011). Similarly, higher levels of interpersonal trust foster a collective sense of agency, mitigating environmental scepticism (Baiardi and Morana 2021). Conversely, erosion of trust and social bonds can induce feelings of discouragement and exacerbate scepticism (Spektor, Fasolin and Camargo 2023).

At the same time, environmental attitudes have been shown to be strong predictors of individuals' scepticism about climate change. In some cases, pre-existing environmental attitudes are the primary factor in predicting climate change scepticism (Engels et al. 2013). Similarly, a preference for nature, sustainability, and care for others or the planet is associated with lower levels of climate change scepticism (Poortinga et al. 2011). Furthermore, adherence to the New Ecological Paradigm is linked to reduced scepticism (Clements 2012).

Besides, research has indicated that exposure to extreme weather events can mitigate climate scepticism. Objectively, a succession of heatwaves (Hornsey, Chapman and Humphrey 2022; Kaufmann et al. 2017) or floods (Munoz-Carrier, Thomsen and Pickering 2020) has correlated with lower levels of climate scepticism, even attenuating the strong influence of partisan politics in the United States on climate scepticism (Usry, Husser and Sparks 2022). Additionally, studies have reported lower levels of climate scepticism among individuals with a higher perceived risk of environmental hazards (Wang and Kim 2018; de Boer, Botzen and Terpstra 2015).

Finally, it has been argued that climate scepticism is not a universal cultural trait but rather is underpinned by processes of cultural scaffolding (Rudiak-Gould 2013). Consequently, climate scepticism has been explained by the difficulty of reconciling this phenomenon with fundamental beliefs such as economic growth, extensive consumption, and the ubiquitous use of automobiles in the case of the United States (Lejano 2019). At the same time, it has been noted that belief in science is associated with lower levels of climate scepticism (Trémolière and Djeriouat 2021), can attenuate partisan cleavages (Bugden 2022), and in some contexts is the most important predictor (Carlton et al. 2014).

This paper examines the evolution of the influence of all the previous factors, including political positioning and ideology, on climate change scepticism in Spain between 2010 and 2023. Notably, there is a limited body of research specifically focused on climate scepticism in Spain. Existing studies have primarily adopted qualitative approaches to analyse scepticism in media discourse (León and Codina 2016; Domínguez, Lafita and Mateu 2017; Jiménez-Gómez and Martín-Sosa 2022) and public discourse (Ramos Torre and Callejo Gallego 2025), with a few quantitative exceptions that explore perceptions of climate risk in coastal tourism settings (March, Saurí and Olcina 2014). The most significant findings for Spain suggest increasing trust in the scientific consensus (Jiménez-Loaisa and Jareño-Ruiz 2024; Ramos Torre and Callejo Gallego 2025) and reduced levels of scepticism (March, Saurí and Olcina 2014; IDEARA 2021; Fraembs and Drobnic 2024). While sociodemographic factors have been identified as influencing climate scepticism (March, Saurí and Olcina 2014; IDEARA 2021), there is also evidence of a growing politicization of these beliefs, with right-leaning sectors exhibiting more scepticism towards scientific consensus (Jiménez-Loaisa and Jareño-Ruiz 2024) and the emergence of interest groups promoting climate change denial (Domínguez, Lafita and Mateu 2017).

To summarise the preceding observations, this paper aims to: 1) assess whether the extent of climate scepticism in Spain has reached the elevated levels observed in the United States and other Anglophone countries; 2) determine whether political factors have become increasingly significant over time in explaining this scepticism in Spain; and 3) provide initial evidence on the evolution of the most significant determinants of climate scepticism in Spain.

3. Data and methods.

To achieve the aforementioned objectives, this study utilised the 'Medio Ambiente (II)' and 'Medio Ambiente III' surveys conducted by the Centre for Sociological Research (Spain) in 2010 and 2023, respectively. Both surveys were administered to a nationally representative sample of individuals aged 18 and over, employing a stratified random sampling technique with municipalities as the stratification units. To ensure comparability over time, the majority of the sequence and questions from the 2010 questionnaire were retained in the 2023 version. The 2010 survey yielded 2560 completed questionnaires, allowing for estimates with a margin of error of +/- 1.98% at a 95.5% confidence level for the total sample. Similarly, the 2023 survey obtained 2254 completed questionnaires, providing estimates with a margin of error of +/- 2.1% at a 95.5% confidence level for the total sample.

As dependent variables, indicative of scepticism towards the effects of climate change, we employed the question included in the 2010 and 2023 questionnaires: 'Overall, how do you

think a rise in global temperature caused by climate change will affect the environment?' To assess levels of scepticism regarding the existence and causes of climate change, we utilized the question:

'Which of the following statements most closely reflects your opinion? The global climate...

1. Has not been changing
2. Has been changing primarily due to natural processes
3. Has been changing due to both natural processes and human activity, in equal proportions
4. Has been changing primarily due to human activity
5. I don't know.'

This question was only included in the 2023 study, and thus could not be considered when analysing the evolution of factors influencing climate change scepticism.

As independent variables, we utilized the variables identified in the literature review that determined the various levels of climate scepticism and were included in the 2010 and 2023 questionnaires. Such variables were grouped into different blocks according to their nature.

The characteristics and values of the variables introduced into the analysis are summarized in the following table.

Table 1. Research variables.

Step	Variable	Level	Values
Dependent	Extent of agreement that the climate change-induced temperature rise poses a significant threat to the environment	Interval	1. Extremely dangerous; 2. Very dangerous; 3. Moderately dangerous; 4. Not very dangerous; 5. Not at all dangerous
	Agreement with statements regarding the existence and causes of planetary climate change	Nominal	1. Remained unchanged; 2. Changed due to natural processes; 3. Changed due to a combination of natural processes and human activities; 4. Changed due to human activities
1. Sociodemographic Factors	Sex (women)	Nominal/dummy	0. Men; 1. Women
	Age	Ratio	
	Level of education	Ordinal	1. No education- 6. Higher education
	Household size	Ratio	
	Marital Status: Single	Nominal/dummy	0. Other status; 1. Single
2. PBC	Population size	Ordinal	1. Less than 2000- 7. More than 1000000
	Agreement with the statement: 'I am uncertain whether my lifestyle is environmentally beneficial or detrimental'	Interval	1. Strongly disagree- 5. Strongly agree
	Agreement with the statement: 'It is very difficult for someone like me to make a difference for the environment'	Interval	1. Strongly disagree- 5. Strongly agree
	Public trust	Interval	1. I am generally cautious in my interactions with others- 5 I believe that most people can be trusted
	Agreement with the statement: 'It is pointless for me to take environmental action unless others do the same'	Interval	1. Strongly disagree- 5. Strongly agree

3. Environmental attitudes	Agreement with the willingness to pay higher prices for environmental protection	Interval	1. Strongly disagree- 5. Strongly agree
	Agreement with the willingness to pay higher taxes for environmental protection	Interval	1. Strongly disagree- 5. Strongly agree
	Agreement with accepting lifestyle reductions for environmental protection.	Interval	1. Strongly disagree- 5. Strongly agree
4. Exposure to environmental problems	Agreement with the statement: 'Environmental problems have an impact on my daily life'	Interval	1. Strongly disagree- 5. Strongly agree
5. Environmental beliefs	Agreement with the statement: 'Almost everything we do harms the environment'	Interval	1. Strongly disagree- 5. Strongly agree
	Agreement with the statement: 'Science will solve environmental problems without requiring us to change our lifestyles'	Interval	1. Strongly disagree- 5. Strongly agree
	Agreement with the statement: 'Economic growth always harms the environment'	Interval	1. Strongly disagree- 5. Strongly agree
6. Political and ideological factors	Position in the political ideology scale	Interval	1. Left – 10. Right
	Voting behaviour in the previous election (right-wing parties)	Nominal/ dummy	0. Other parties; 1. Right-wing parties (VOX, Partido Popular, Ciudadanos)
	Agreement with the statement: 'The private enterprise is the most effective means of addressing economic challenges'	Interval	1. Strongly disagree- 5. Strongly agree
	Agreement with the statement: 'The government is responsible for reducing income inequality'	Interval	1. Strongly disagree- 5. Strongly agree

Descriptive statistics were employed to assess the prevalence of climate change denialism in 2023. Additionally, descriptive statistics were used to examine the perceived effects of climate change in 2010 and 2023.

Hierarchical multiple regression models were then applied to investigate the factors influencing scepticism towards the effects of climate change in both years. By sequentially entering different blocks of variables into the hierarchical regression model, we were able to evaluate the incremental contribution of each block to model fit and the impact on the predictive power of previously included variables. As noted by Cohen (2001), hierarchical multiple regression is well-suited for assessing the unique contribution of predictors by comparing their contribution to the model with that of predictors entered at earlier steps.

Prior to conducting hierarchical multiple regression, the model's assumptions were assessed. Regarding multicollinearity, correlations among predictors were examined and found not to exceed the threshold of $r = 0.7$ as stipulated by Tabachnick and Fidell (2019). Similarly, collinearity diagnostics yielded variance inflation factor (VIF) values below 10. To identify outliers, standardised residual plots were inspected, revealing no extremely high or low values. Moreover, only 7 observations in the 2010 sample and 8 in the 2023 sample exhibited standardised residual values exceeding the ± 3.3 threshold recommended by Tabachnick and Fidell (2019). Normal probability plots for both 2010 and 2023 showed no substantial

deviations from the diagonal line, indicating normality. Scatterplots of standardised residuals for both years also aligned with the central distribution, as suggested by Tabachnick and Fidell (2019), thus confirming adherence to residual assumptions.

The entry of predictor blocks adhered to the sequence outlined in Table 1. When introducing different blocks, we prioritized the inclusion of sociodemographic variables first and ensured that, in cases of potential interactions between predictors, the causal block was entered before the effects block, following Petrocelli's (2003) recommendation. This was the case for the environmental exposure factor, which was assumed to condition the emergence of the environmental beliefs block and was therefore placed at an earlier stage. The final block to be entered in the model was that of political and ideological factors, as these predictor variables were the primary focus of this article. Analyses were conducted using SPSS version 29.

4. Results.

Only the 2023 CIS survey included a question allowing for the assessment of scepticism regarding the evolution and causes of climate change. The analysis revealed a very low prevalence of explicitly sceptical views (Table 2), with only 1.99% of respondents denying the existence of climate change and 4.97% suggesting that, while climate change was occurring, it was primarily driven by natural rather than human factors. However, it should also be noted that positions aligned with the scientific consensus affirming anthropogenic climate change were slightly below 66% (Table 2).

Table 2. Statement with which respondents most agree regarding global climate. 2023.

Statement	Agreement (%)
Remained unchanged	1.99%
Changed due to natural processes	4.97%
Changed due to a combination of natural processes and human activities	27.05%
Changed due to human activities	65.98%

Source: Own analysis based on the ‘Encuesta Medio Ambiente III’, Centre for Sociological Research

The third dimension of climate scepticism regarding the severity of climate change impacts was included in the CIS surveys of 2010 and 2023. As shown in Table 3, the proportion of respondents indicating that the increase in global temperature was not at all or not very dangerous was 4.25% in 2010, rising slightly to 4.46% in 2023. The data also reveal an increase in the proportion of individuals who considered the rise in global temperature to be extremely dangerous, from 29.51% in 2010 to 39.55% in 2023 (Table 3). The slight increase in positions corresponding to climate scepticism, coupled with a significant increase in those attributing the highest level of danger to climate change, suggests a polarisation in these attitudes. By converting this ordinal scale variable on the danger of global temperature increase to a continuous scale, the standard deviation from the mean could be calculated. This value was 0.84 in 2010 and 0.88 in 2023 (Table 3), confirming greater dispersion and polarisation of attitudes towards the effects of global temperature increase.

Table 3. Environmental risk associated with global temperature rise. Percentage change between 2010 and 2023.

	2010	2023
Not at all dangerous	1.09%	1.44%
Not very dangerous	3.15%	3.02%
Moderately dangerous	19.28%	15.60%
Very dangerous	46.97%	40.38%
Extremely dangerous	29.51%	39.55%
Mean (1-5 scale)	4.00	4.1
Standard deviation	0.84%	0.88

Source: Own analysis based on the ‘Encuesta Medio Ambiente II’ and ‘Encuesta Medio Ambiente III’, Centre for Sociological Research.

This study could only examine the evolution of factors explaining climate change scepticism in relation to the scepticism about its effects. Questions that would have allowed for an assessment of the evolution of scepticism regarding the causes and the very existence of climate change were only included in the survey from 2023 onwards.

To investigate the evolution of the relative importance of different predictors of climate change scepticism, hierarchical multiple regressions were conducted in 2010 and 2023. The aim was to identify the factors that exerted the greatest influence in explaining the variance of the dependent variable, the perceived danger of rising temperatures, and to determine whether these factors differed between 2010 and 2023. Predictor variables were entered in blocks to assess their incremental contribution to explaining the dependent variable. For comparative purposes, predictor selection was restricted to questions included in both the 2010 and 2023 surveys.

A summary of the hierarchical multiple regression models explaining the scale of climate scepticism for the years 2010 and 2023 is presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Summary of hierarchical multiple regression models explaining the scale of denialism. Years 2010 and 2023.

Model	2010				2023			
	R	R Square	R square change	Sig. F change	R	R Square	R square change	Sig. F change
1. Sociodemographic Factors	0.168	0.028	0.028	0.000	0.136	0.018	0.018	0.002
2. PBC	0.188	0.035	0.007	0.064	0.225	0.051	0.032	0.000
3. Attitudes	0.224	0.050	0.015	0.000	0.375	0.140	0.090	0.000
4. Exposure	0.262	0.068	0.018	0.000	0.482	0.232	0.092	0.000
5. Beliefs	0.328	0.107	0.039	0.000	0.593	0.352	0.119	0.000
6. Political and ideological factors	0.362	0.131	0.024	0.000	0.629	0.395	0.043	0.000

Source: Own analysis based on the Encuesta Medio Ambiente II and Encuesta Medio Ambiente III, Centre for Sociological Research.

A significant improvement in the predictive capacity of models to estimate the hazard associated with rising temperatures is evident when comparing those developed for 2023 with those for 2010. The latest model, incorporating all variables in 2023, explained 39.5% of the variance in the dependent variable, compared to only 13.1% for the 2010 model (see Table 4).

Both the 2010 model, $F(21, 1229) = 8,658, p < 0.001$, and the 2023 model, $F(21, 1097) = 33,456, p < 0.001$, were statistically significant. Thus, it can be inferred that the various explanatory factors have increasingly accounted for scepticism regarding the effects of climate change over time.

Furthermore, it is noteworthy that, in the Spanish context, variables related to political ideology were less significant in explaining climate change scepticism than suggested by studies of other countries. Specifically, in 2010, this set of variables ranked third in importance, contributing a 2.4% increase to the model's explanatory power, while in 2023 it ranked fourth, contributing a 4.3% increase (Table 4). In 2010, variables related to environmental beliefs and sociodemographic factors were more influential, respectively. In 2023, variables related to environmental beliefs, perceived exposure to environmental problems, and environmental attitudes contributed greater increases to the explanation of the scepticism scale.

A substantial change in the explanatory power of various factors underlying climate change scepticism was observed between 2010 and 2023. Although environmental beliefs remained the most consistent predictor of scepticism, sociodemographic factors demonstrated a notable decrease in their predictive capacity. These factors, which were the second most influential in 2010, became the least significant in 2023 (Table 4). In contrast, perceived exposure to environmental issues increased in importance, from the fourth to the second most influential factor in 2023. Moreover, environmental attitudes rose from the fifth to the third most important predictor of climate change scepticism.

To evaluate the independent contributions of each variable in explaining the scepticism scale, Table 5 presents the hierarchical multiple regression coefficients for both 2010 and 2023

Table 5. Coefficients from hierarchical multiple regression models explaining the scale of climate change scepticism. Years 2010 and 2023.

	2010				2023			
	B	Std. Error	Std. B.	Sig.	B	Std. Error	Std. B.	Sig.
Constant	2.565	0.285		0.000	2.727	0.261		0.000
Women	-0.049	0.048	-0.028	0.306	-0.073	0.044	-0.041	0.095
Age	0.005	0.002	0.097	0.006	0.006	0.002	0.105	0.002
Level of education	0.017	0.018	0.029	0.367	0.019	0.012	0.042	0.118
Household size	-0.006	0.020	-0.008	0.775	-0.041	0.020	-0.053	0.041
Single people	-0.062	0.065	-0.031	0.336	0.016	0.061	0.008	0.789
Population size	-0.003	0.001	-0.068	0.017	-0.011	0.013	-0.021	0.381
Uncertain whether my lifestyle is environmentally beneficial or detrimental	0.040	0.024	0.049	0.086	0.031	0.023	0.034	0.174
It is difficult for someone like me to make a difference for the environment'	0.024	0.023	0.031	0.299	0.020	0.023	0.024	0.387
Public trust	0.005	0.022	0.006	0.822	-0.013	0.020	-0.017	0.509
It is pointless for me to take environmental action unless others do the same	-0.029	0.020	-0.043	0.150	0.020	0.020	0.027	0.324
Willingness to pay higher prices for environmental protection	-0.010	0.031	-0.013	0.739	-0.128	0.033	-0.154	0.000

Willingness to pay higher taxes for environmental protection	-0.010	0.032	-0.013	0.757	0.048	0.033	0.061	0.142
Accepting lifestyle reductions for environmental protection.	-0.037	0.027	-0.048	0.172	-0.023	0.027	-0.029	0.401
Environmental problems have an impact on my daily life	-0.061	0.023	-0.078	0.007	-0.163	0.024	-0.185	0.000
Almost everything we do harms the environment	-0.164	0.025	-0.193	0.000	-0.234	0.024	-0.266	0.000
Science will solve environmental problems without requiring us to change our lifestyles	0.007	0.023	0.008	0.767	0.131	0.024	0.140	0.000
Economic growth always harms the environment	0.007	0.024	0.009	0.758	-0.004	0.024	-0.004	0.883
Political ideology scale	0.015	0.017	0.031	0.378	0.028	0.010	0.086	0.005
Voting right-wing parties	0.053	0.067	0.027	0.427	0.006	0.003	0.058	0.018
The private enterprise is the most effective means of addressing economic challenges	0.065	0.022	0.086	0.003	0.044	0.022	0.059	0.046
The government is responsible for reducing income inequality	-0.074	0.023	-0.091	0.001	-0.091	0.021	-0.130	0.000

Source: Own analysis based on the 'Encuesta Medio Ambiente II' and 'Encuesta Medio Ambiente III', Centre for Sociological Research.

Consistent with our earlier model summaries from 2010 and 2023, the coefficients indicate that variables related to political orientation and ideology were not the most significant individual predictors of climate scepticism. However, the coefficients do confirm the direction of the relationships suggested in the literature. Specifically, in 2023, voting for right-wing parties or self-positioning further to the right on the ideological scale was associated with higher levels of climate scepticism (Std. B=0.058, $p < 0.05$ and Std. B=0.086, $p < 0.05$, respectively), while holding pro-interventionist state views, particularly regarding government responsibility for reducing income inequality, was associated with lower levels of climate scepticism (Std. B=-0.130, $p < 0.001$). Despite these findings, other variables proved to be more influential in explaining climate scepticism in both 2010 and 2023. These included beliefs such as 'Almost everything we do harms the environment' and agreement with the statement 'Environmental problems affect my daily life', along with certain sociodemographic variables in 2010 and additional environmental belief variables in 2023.

Table 5 also reveals notable shifts in the individual predictive power of variables in explaining the scale of climate change scepticism. Overall, a greater number of variables were found to be significant predictors of scepticism in 2023. While only six variables were significant in 2010, this increased to ten in 2023. Environmental beliefs demonstrated a strengthened role in individually predicting scepticism in 2023. For instance, agreement with the statement 'Almost everything we do harms the environment' was associated with lower levels of scepticism in both years (std. B = -0.266, $p < 0.001$ in 2023; std. B = -0.193, $p < 0.001$ in 2010). Conversely, agreement with the belief that 'Science will solve environmental problems

without us having to change our lifestyle' emerged as a significant predictor of higher levels of scepticism in 2023 (std. B = 0.140, $p < 0.001$), a relationship that was not observed in 2010.

Furthermore, a significant improvement was observed in the predictive power of the variable concerning the perception that environmental problems affect daily life in 2023 (std. B = -0.185, $p < 0.001$), compared to 2010 (std. B = -0.078, $p < 0.05$) (Table 5). The negative coefficient indicated that individuals who perceived a lesser impact on their daily lives scored higher on the climate change scepticism scale. Additionally, the variable measuring the attitude of paying significantly higher prices to protect the environment, which was not a significant predictor in 2010, became statistically significant in 2023 (std. B = -0.156, $p < 0.001$). The negative sign implied that those who expressed greater willingness to make such sacrifices were less likely to be climate change sceptics.

Finally, in 2023, there was no evidence that some of the sociodemographic variables which explained the dependent variable significantly but marginally in 2010 became more determinant in this explanation. Age maintained similar positive coefficients (std. B=0.097, $p < 0.5$ in 2010 and std. B=0.105, $p < 0.05$ in 2023), indicating that older populations consistently expressed higher levels of climate scepticism in both years. Household size became a significant but minor predictor of this scale in 2023, while population size ceased to be a significant explanatory factor for climate change scepticism in 2023 (Table 5).

Other variables identified in the literature as important in explaining climate change scepticism, such as perceived personal and collective efficacy and control over one's own actions, were not found to be significant in either 2010 or 2023 (Table 5).

5. Discussion.

The primary contribution of our findings is to demonstrate the low levels of climate scepticism in Spain. In 2023, a mere 1.99% of the population denied that the planet's climate was changing, and only 4.97% attributed such changes to natural causes alone. Moreover, between 2010 and 2023, scepticism regarding the severity of climate change consequences remained minimal: those who asserted that the increase in Earth's temperature was not very or not at all dangerous constituted 4.24% of the population in 2010 and 4.46% in 2023. However, results indicate a slight polarisation of positions on the severity of these effects, evidenced by a growing standard deviation of the means, which increased from 0.84 points in 2010 to 0.88 in 2023. These data contrast starkly with those from the United States, where in 2024, 13% of individuals denied climate change, and 23% rejected the notion of anthropogenic causes. Similarly, European figures stood at 10% and 22% respectively (IPSOS 2024). Consequently, it can be concluded that the prevalence of climate scepticism does not yet pose a significant problem in Spain.

Secondly, political factors appeared to be less influential in shaping climate change scepticism in Spain compared to the United States and other Anglophone nations. Furthermore, their influence has waned over time. In 2010, political factors constituted the third most significant set of factors, accounting for 2.4% of the 13.1% of total scepticism variance explained by the model. By 2023, these factors had dropped to the fourth most important position, explaining 4.3% of the 39.5% of total scepticism variance accounted for by the 2023

model. These findings corroborate previous research (Ziegler 2017; Lewis, Pal and Feng 2018), suggesting that the strong correlation between political ideology and climate scepticism observed in the United States may be a country-specific phenomenon, and that a wider range of factors may be at play in other nations.

While not the most significant factors, our findings demonstrate that ideological and political variables could meaningfully explain climate scepticism in 2023. In this year, holding right-wing ideological positions, voting for right-wing parties, or endorsing right-wing propositions was associated with higher levels of scepticism about the dangers of climate change. These results underscore the need for continued vigilance regarding potential ideological polarisation in responses to climate change. They corroborate the growing body of evidence in the Spanish context (IDEARA 2021; Jiménez-Loaisa and Jareño-Ruiz 2024), and suggest that this trend could intensify with the rise of the far-right party VOX, mirroring patterns observed in other countries such as Germany with the AfD (Knollenborg and Sommer 2022).

Thirdly, these findings provide initial evidence of the determinants of climate scepticism in Spain. Specifically, data from 2010 and 2023 confirmed the predominance of certain environmental beliefs in explaining scepticism about the dangers of climate change. The belief that 'Almost everything we do harms the environment' was the strongest predictor of lower levels of climate scepticism in both 2010 and 2023. Furthermore, opposition to the belief that 'Science will solve most environmental problems without the need to change our way of life' was also a significant predictor of lower levels of climate scepticism, particularly in 2023. This Spanish evidence aligns with findings from other countries such as the United Kingdom, where a set of environmental values emerged as the most significant determinants of climate scepticism (Clements 2012). These results highlight the need to carefully align institutional messaging on science and climate change with these values to ensure its effectiveness and comprehensibility, as suggested by Furnham (2024) and Agrell (2012).

Our findings underscore the salient role of perceived exposure to environmental problems in predicting climate scepticism. Specifically, the recognition that environmental issues significantly impact daily life was associated with reduced climate scepticism in both 2010 and 2023, emerging as the second most influential factor in the latter year. These results resonate with evidence from other contexts, such as the Netherlands (de Boer, Botzen and Terpstra 2015), where heightened exposure to potential flooding correlates with increased public awareness of climate change risks. In the Spanish context, given projections of high climate change exposure (Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica 2020; Arellano, Roca and Zheng 2024), this relationship could potentially mitigate the prevalence of sceptical attitudes towards climate change.

However, the efficacy of this relationship hinges on the recognition of environmental exposure as such. In this regard, Botzen et al. (2016) have demonstrated that the acknowledgement of environmental exposure is itself contingent upon citizens' political and ideological orientations. Consequently, it is imperative to investigate whether, in the Spanish case, ideological and political affiliations may introduce biases in the perception of

environmental problems, thereby precluding a segment of the electorate from acknowledging environmental risks and aligning with climate-sceptic stances.

This paper has provided initial evidence of the primary factors influencing climate change scepticism in Spain, which warrants further investigation. Of particular importance will be monitoring the potential politicization of climate scepticism in Spain following the emergence of a far-right party that has adopted this stance as a core ideological principle. It will be crucial to observe whether the consolidation of these positions at the extreme end of the political spectrum translates into a significant rise in scepticism, as seen in the United States through what has been called the 'echo chamber effect' (Carmichael, Brulle and Huxster 2017). Furthermore, future research could delve deeper into the specific types of environmental beliefs and exposures to climate change that correlate with lower levels of climate scepticism, incorporating a wider range of variables in this regard. In the case of exposure to environmental problems, it would be beneficial to assess the particular type of climate change impact that most effectively inhibits the development of scepticism.

While the Centre for Sociological Research databases upon which this article is based are of excellent quality, a significant limitation of the scope of these findings lies in the inclusion of the question on the existence and anthropogenic causes of climate change solely in the 2023 questionnaire. The absence of this question in the 2010 questionnaire prevented the observation of temporal trends in both trend and attribution scepticism towards climate change, which other studies have shown to be highly significant. Consequently, only the evolution of scepticism regarding the impacts of climate change could be assessed. It is anticipated that the introduction of this question in future questionnaires will enable more detailed studies of changes and causes in these other dimensions of climate change scepticism.

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Data Availability:

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available at [https://www.cis.es/references:2837 and 3391](https://www.cis.es/references:2837and3391)

References.

- Aerni, P., Gaglac, F., Scholderer, J. (2016) 'The role of biotechnology in combating climate change: A question of politics?', *Science and Public Policy*, 43(1): 13-28. <https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scv014>
- Agrell, W. (2012) 'Framing prospects and risk in the public promotion of ESS in Scandinavia', *Science and Public Policy*, 39: 429-438. <https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scs045>
- Aitken, M., Cunningham-Burley, S., and Pagliari, C. (2016) 'Moving from trust to trustworthiness: Experiences of public engagement in the Scottish Health Informatics Programme', *Science and Public Policy* 43(5): 713-723. <https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scv075>

- Arellano, B., Roca, J., and Zheng, Q. (2020) *Spain: Towards a Drier and Warmer Climate? Analysis of Climate Change Effects on Precipitation and Temperature Trends in Spain*. Barcelona: Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya.
- Ashe, T., and Poberezhskaya, M. (2022) 'Russian climate scepticism: an understudied case', *Climatic Change*, 172: 41. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-022-03390-3>.
- Baiardi, D., and Morana, C. (2021) 'Climate change awareness: Empirical evidence from the European Union', *Energy Economics*, 96: 105163. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2021.105163>
- Bevacqua, E., Schleussner, C.-F., and Zscheishler, J. (2025) 'A year above 1.5 °C signals that Earth is most probably within the 20-year period that will reach the Paris Agreement limit', *Nature Climate Change*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-025-02246-9>
- Boncu, S., Prundeanu, O., Holman, A. C., and Popusoi, S. A. (2022) 'Believing in or Denying Climate Change for Questionable Reasons: Generic Conspiracist Beliefs, Personality, and Climate Change Perceptions of Romanian University Students', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19: 17038. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph192417038>
- Borger, J. (2001, March 29) 'Bush kill global warming treaty', *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/environment/2001/mar/29/globalwarming.usnews>
- Botzen, W. J., Wouter, M. K., Kunreuther, H., de Moel, H., and Aerts, J. C. J. H. (2016) 'Political affiliation affects adaptation to climate risks: Evidence from New York City', *Climatic Change*, 138: 353-360. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-016-1735-9>
- Bugden, D. (2022) 'Denial and distrust: explaining the partisan climate gap', *Climatic Change*, 170: 34. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-022-03321-2>
- Carlton, J. S., Perry-Hill, R., Huber, M., and Prokopy, L. S. (2015) 'The climate change consensus extends beyond climate scientists', *Environmental Research Letters*, 10: 094025. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/10/9/094025>
- Carmichael, J. T., Brulle, R. J., and Huxster, J. K. (2017) 'The great divide: understanding the role of media and other drivers of the partisan divide in public concern over climate change in the USA, 2001–2014', *Climatic Change*, 141: 599-612. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-017-1908-1>
- Clements, B. (2012) 'Exploring public opinion on the issue of climate change in Britain', *British Politics*, 7: 183-202. <https://doi.org/10.1057/bp.2012.1>
- Cohen, B. H. (2001) *Explaining Psychological Statistics*. New York: Wiley.
- de Boer, J., Botzen, W. J. W., and Terpstra, T. (2015) 'Flood risk and climate change in the Rotterdam area, The Netherlands: enhancing citizen's climate risk perceptions and prevention responses despite skepticism', *Regional Environmental Change*, 16: 1613-1622. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-015-0900-4>
- Domínguez, M., Lafita, I., and Mateu, A. (2017) 'Taking climate change seriously: An analysis of op-ed articles in Spanish press', *Public Understanding of Science*, 26(7): 861-871. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0963662516641844>

- Ecklund, E., Howard, S., Christopher, P., Peifer, J., and Bolger, D. (2017) 'Examining Links Between Religion, Evolution Views, and Climate Change Skepticism', *Environment and Behavior*, 49(9): 985-1006. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013916516674246>
- Engels, A., Hüther, O., Schäfer, M., and Held, H. (2013) 'Public climate-change skepticism, energy preferences and political participation', *Global Environmental Change*, 23: 1018-1027. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2013.05.008>
- Fraembs, T. V., and Drobnic, S. (2024) 'Il-informed or ideologically driven? Climate change awareness and denial in Europe', *Population and Environment*, 46: 21. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11111-024-00462-7>
- Furnham, A. (2024) 'Sustainability Skepticism: Attitudes to, and Beliefs about Climate Change', *Sustainability*, 16: 8164. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16188164>
- Gallup (2024) *Are Americans Concerned About Global Warming?* <https://news.gallup.com/poll/355427/americans-concerned-global-warming.aspx>. Accessed 14 February 2025.
- Grobe, S. (2017, March 28) 'Trump burns down Obama's climate legacy', *Euronews*. <https://www.euronews.com/2017/03/28/trump-burns-down-obamas-climate-legacy>. Accessed 14 February 2025.
- Haglin, K., and Vedlitz, A. (2023) 'Ideology, knowledge, and the assessment of science policy agencies', *Science and Public Policy*, 50(4): 707-718. <https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scad020>
- Hahnel, U. J. J., Mumenthaler, C., and Brosch, T. (2019) 'Emotional foundations of the public climate change divide', *Climatic Change*, 161: 9-19. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-019-02552-0>
- Hornsey, M., Chapman, C. M., and Humphrey, J. E. (2022) 'Climate skepticism decreases when the planet gets hotter and conservative support wanes', *Global Environmental Change*, 74: 102492. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2022.102492>
- IDEARA (2021) *La sociedad española ante el cambio climático. Percepción y comportamientos de la población*. Madrid: IDEARA.
- IPSOS (2024) *Obs' COP 2024 World opinion in the face of climate change*. https://www.edf.fr/sites/groupe/files/2024-11/obscop2024_fichier_tris-croises_en.xlsx. Accessed 12 February 2025.
- Jiménez-Gómez, I., and Martín-Sosa, S. (2022) 'Análisis discursivo del escepticismo climático en los medios impresos y digitales españoles entre 2015 y 2021' *Estudios sobre el Mensaje Periodístico*, 28(3): 525-536. <https://dx.doi.org/10.5209/esmp.80779>
- Jiménez-Loaisa, F. J., Jareño-Ruiz, D. (2024) 'Polarización ideológica en torno a la ciencia en España: el caso de las actitudes anticientíficas, las creencias conspirativas y la confianza en los científicos', *Methaodos. Revista de ciencias sociales*, 12(2): m241202a03. <https://doi.org/10.17502/mrcs.v12i2.821>
- Kaufmann, R. K., Mann, M. L., Gopal, S., Liederman, J. A., Howe, P. D., Pretis, F., Tang, X., and Gilmore, M. (2017) 'Spatial heterogeneity of climate change as an experiential basis for skepticism'. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 114(1): 67-71. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1607032113>

- Knollenborg, L., and Sommer, S. (2022) 'Driving Beliefs of Climate Change and Climate Policy: The Role of Political Orientation', *Environmental and Resource Economics*, 84: 1031-1049. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10640-022-00747-1>
- Leka, J., and Furnham, A. (2024) 'Correlates of climate change skepticism', *Frontiers in Psychology*, 15: 1328307. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2024.1328307>
- Lejano, R. P. (2019) 'Ideology and the Narrative of Climate Skepticism', *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Association*, 100(12): ES415-ES421. <https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-16-0327.1>
- León, B., and Codina, M. (2016) 'Information and opinion in the representation of scientific consensus and skepticism on climate change, in Spanish language online publications', *Observatorio (OBS) Journal*, 10(3): 104-118. <https://doi.org/10.7458/OBS10320161021>
- Lewis, G. B., Palm, R., and Feng, B. (2018) 'Cross-national variation in determinants of climate change concern', *Environmental Politics*, 28(5): 793-821. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09644016.2018.1512261>
- Liu, J. C.-E. (2015) 'Low carbon plot: climate change skepticism with Chinese characteristics', *Environmental Sociology*, 1(4): 280-292. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23251042.2015.1049811>
- Lloyd, I. (1996) 'Science and public policy -has the 20th century made any progress?', *Science and Public Policy*, 23(1): 55-58.
- March, H., Saurí, D., and Olcina, J. (2014) 'Rising Temperatures and Dwindling Water Supplies? Perception of Climate Change Among Residents of the Spanish Mediterranean Tourist Coastal Areas', *Environmental Management*, 53: 181-193. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00267-013-0177-7>
- Marteau, T. M., (2023) 'Evidence-neglect: addressing a barrier to UK health and climate policy ambitions', *Science and Public Policy*, 50: 1103-1109. <https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scad021>
- Matthews, P. (2015) 'Why Are People Skeptical about Climate Change? Some Insights from Blog Comments', *Environmental Communication*, 9(2): 153-168. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/17524032.2014.999694>
- McCright, A. M. (2016) 'Anti-Reflexivity and Climate Change Skepticism in the US General Public', *Human Ecology Review*, 22(2): 77-107. <https://doi.org/10.4225/13/58213a5387787>
- McCright, A. M., and Dunlap, R. E. (2011) 'The politicization of climate change and polarization in the American public's views of global warming, 2001-2010' *The Sociological Quarterly*, 52: 155-194. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1533-8525.2011.01198.x>
- Meyer, A. G. (2018) 'Elite Influence on Climate Change Skepticism: Evidence from Close Gubernatorial Elections', *Journal of the Association of Environmental and Resource Economists*, 6(4): 783-822. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1086/703744>
- Miller, J.D., Laspra, B., Polino, C., Branch, G., Ackerman, M. S., Pennock, R. T. (2024) 'Citizen attitudes toward science and technology, 1957–2020: measurement, stability, and the Trump challenge', *Science and Public Policy*, 51: 526-542. <https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scad086>
- Milman, O., Smith, D., and Carrington, D. (2017, June 1) 'Donald Trump confirms US will quit Paris climate agreement', *The Guardian*.

<https://www.theguardian.com/environment/2017/jun/01/donald-trump-confirms-us-will-quit-paris-climate-deal>. Accessed 14 February 2025.

-Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica (2020) *Plan Nacional de Adaptación al Cambio Climático 2021-2030*. Madrid: Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica.

-Munoz-Carrier, G., Thomsen, D., Pickering, G.J. (2020) 'Psychological and experiential factors affecting climate change perception: learnings from a transnational empirical study and implications for framing climate-related flood events', *Environmental Research Communications*, 2: 045003. <https://doi.org/10.1088/2515-7620/ab89f9>

-Ojala, M. (2015) 'Climate change eskepticism among adolescents', *Journal of Youth Studies*, 18(9): 1135-1153. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/13676261.2015.1020927>

-Pano, A., and Carrus, G. (2019) 'Attitudes towards Trump Policies and Climate Change: The Key Roles of Aversion to Wealth Redistribution and Political Interest', *Journal of Social Issues*, 75(1): 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.1111/josi.12318>

-Pellegrini, G., and Loner, E. (2024) 'Italians and Global Warming Skepticism: opinions and Ways of information', *Observatorio (OBS) Journal*, 18(6): 43-63. <https://doi.org/10.15847/obsOBS18520242574>

-Pew Research Center (2022) *Americans Largely Favor U.S. Taking Steps To Become Carbon Neutral by 2050*. Washington. https://www.pewresearch.org/wp-content/uploads/sites/20/2022/02/PS_2022.03.01_carbon-neutral-2050_REPORT.pdf

-Pianin, E., and Goldstein, A. (2001, March 13) 'Bush drops a call for emissions cuts', *The Washington Post*. <https://www.washingtonpost.com/archive/politics/2001/03/14/bush-drops-a-call-for-emissions-cuts/cbfe9644-0586-4cff-93a9-66446e4c07bd/>. Accessed 14 February 2025.

-Poortinga, W., Spence, A., Whitmarsh, L., Capstick, S., and Pidgeon, N. F. (2011) 'Uncertain climate: An investigation into public scepticism about anthropogenic climate change', *Global Environmental Change*, 21: 1015-1024. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2011.03.001>

-Ramos Torre, R., and Callejo Gallego, J., (2025) 'Cambio climático e incertidumbres dóxicas. Entre el negacionismo y el activismo', *Papers*, 110(1): 1-24. <https://doi.org/10.5565/rev/papers.3329>

-Rudiak-Gould, P. (2013) 'Cross-cultural insights into climate change skepticism', *Bulleting of the American Meteorological Association*, 94(11): 1707-1713. <https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-12-00129.1>

-Santos, J. M., and Feygina, I. (2017) 'Responding to Climate Change Skepticism and the Ideological Divide', *Michigan Journal of Sustainability*, 5(1): 5-22. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3998/mjs.12333712.0005.102>

-Schmidt, C. W. (2010) 'A Closer Look at Climate Change Skepticism', *Environmental Health Perspectives*, 118(12): 536-540. <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.118-a536>

-Smith, N., and Leiserowitz, A. (2015) 'The Rise of Global Warming Skepticism: Exploring Affective Image Associations in the United States Over Time', *Risk Analysis*, 32(6): 1021-1032. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1539-6924.2012.01801.x>

-Spektor, M., Fasolin, G., and Camargo, J. (2023) 'Climate change beliefs and their correlates in Latin America', *Nature Communications*, 14: 7291. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-42729-x>

- Stevenson, K. T., Peterson, M., Nils, B., Howard, M., Susan, E., and Carrier, S. J. (2014) 'Overcoming skepticism with education: interacting influences of worldview and climate change knowledge on perceived climate change risk among adolescents', *Climatic Change*, 126: 293-304. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-014-1228-7>
- Tabachnick, B. G., and Fidell, L. S. (2019) *Using Multivariate Statistics*. London: Pearson.
- Trémolière, B., and Djeriouat, H. (2021) 'Exploring the roles of analytic cognitive style, climate science literacy, illusion of knowledge, and political orientation in climate change skepticism', *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 74: 101561. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2021.101561>
- Usry, K., Husser, J., and Sparks, A. (2022) 'I'm Not a Scientist, I Just Know What I See: Hurricane experience and climate change acceptance', *Social Science Quarterly*, 103: 1190-1201. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ssqu.13196>
- Wang, J., and Kim, S. (2018) 'Analysis of the Impact of Values and Perception on Climate Change Skepticism and Its Implication for Public Policy', *Climate*, 6: 99. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cli6040099>
- Whitmarsh, L. (2011) 'Scepticism and uncertainty about climate change: Dimensions, determinants and change over time', *Global Environmental Change*, 21: 690-700. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2011.01.016>
- World Meteorological Organization (2025) *WMO confirms 2024 as warmest year on record at about 1.55°C above pre-industrial level*. <https://wmo.int/news/media-centre/wmo-confirms-2024-warmest-year-record-about-155degc-above-pre-industrial-level> Accessed 14 February 2025.
- Yan, P., Schroeder, R., and Stier, S. (2022) 'Is there a link between climate change scepticism and populism? An analysis of web tracking and survey data from Europe and the US', *Information, Communication and Society*, 25(10): 1400-1439. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369118X.2020.1864005>
- Yang, J., Gounaridis, D., Liu, M., Bi, J., and Newll, J. (2021) 'Perceptions of Climate Change in China: Evidence From Surveys of Residents in Six Cities', *Earth's Future*, 9: e2021EF002144. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021EF002144>.
- Ziegler, A. (2017) 'Political orientation, environmental values, and climate change beliefs and attitudes: An empirical cross country analysis', *Energy Economics*, 63: 144-153. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2017.01.022>